

worm

**Waste in humanitarian Operations:
Reduction and Minimisation**

D5.1. SOPs for Product Use, Reuse, Recycling, Reverse Logistics, and Recovery in Field Hospitals and EMTs

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	FULL NAME
EC	European Commission
EMT	Emergency Medical Team
ERP	Enterprise resource planning
FRC	Finnish Red Cross
LCA	Life cycle assessment
LCC	Life cycle costing
LCCA	Life cycle cost assessment
PPE	Personal protective equipment
QSE	Quality, safety, and environment
RFQ	Request for quotation
SOP	Standard operating procedure
WASH	Water, sanitation, and hygiene
WHO	World Health Organization
WM	Waste management
WMC	Waste management committee
WPs	Work Packages

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BACKGROUND ABOUT WORM

WORM aims to design guidelines and support actions for circular economy in the humanitarian sector. It integrates bio-based technological solutions, leverages procurement to reduce waste, improves waste management practices, and prioritises the sustainable livelihoods of waste pickers. WORM focuses on two selected settings: field hospital deployments and humanitarian livelihood programmes with a waste-picking component. Following a collaborative, multi-actor approach, WORM brings together medical and humanitarian organisations, procurement service providers, logistics providers, waste management services, and academic partners.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the WORM Project, funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101135392.

This document aims to provide standardised guidelines for more circular use of materials and products, as well as appropriate waste management for emergency medical teams and field hospitals. Waste from medical facilities requires careful segregation to ensure safe disposal for both public health and the environment. Many current disposal methods, especially in precarious contexts where field hospitals are often deployed, do not meet health and safety standards. Open burning and unregulated incineration, as well as improper disposal of fossil-fuel-based materials, generate air pollution and release harmful particulate matter into the environment.

These SOPs focus on needs-based product use at the field-operation level. Procurement decisions and guidelines (D2.2) are therefore highly influential for the SOPs. This document provides clear guidelines for the sustainable use of equipment and materials to minimise waste, along with reuse, maintenance and repair processes. Many of these processes require collaboration with local partners, including waste management companies, recycling facilities, informal waste pickers, and equipment and material suppliers. These partnerships will carry over with the handover process, for which WORM has compiled an additional set of SOPs (D5.3)

These SOPs follow the guiding principle of humanitarian aid: do no harm. WORM extends the do-no-harm principle to the environment by implementing circularity and sustainability into processes by design. The SOPs also ensure accountability and transparency throughout the process, thanks to the standardisation opportunity throughout the sector.

NON-TECHNICAL SUMMARY

This document is part of the WORM Project, funded by the EU's Horizon Europe programme. It provides clear guidelines to help emergency medical teams and field hospitals manage materials and waste in a more sustainable and safe way. Medical waste needs careful handling to protect both public health and the environment, but in many field settings, current practices like open burning or unregulated incineration cause pollution and health risks.

The guidelines focus on reducing waste through more innovative use of products, reuse, maintenance, and repair. They also emphasize working with local partners such as recycling facilities and waste management services to ensure proper disposal and sustainability. By following these standardized procedures, the project aims to uphold humanitarian principles, extend "do no harm" to the environment, and promote accountability and transparency across the sector.

INTRODUCTION

These SOPs (D5.1, D5.2) operationalise WORM’s research into a practical tool that can be harnessed in field hospital contexts across the sector. The principles and broader objectives of WORM, and the SOPs as the operationalising element, are summarised in Figure 1. The defining goal is to demonstrate that humanitarian response can be sustainable and circular without compromising financial security. A crucial step in achieving this is to establish sustainable and circular WM as a core operational function in a humanitarian operation. Medical WM guidelines for use in operations have been outlined in WORM D5.3. The SOPs integrate field-based knowledge and strategic objectives into an operational document which can be used as a basis for training, practical field-based activities in EMT deployments, and the handover of the field hospital to local partners (D5.2). Local engagement is paramount, as contextual differences in deployments are significant and WM activities, such as recycling, require local partnerships.

Figure 1 WORM and SOP objectives

Inadequate WM can cause numerous environmental and societal issues. The WHO therefore recommends standardization and national legislation to enable WM practices, particularly when it comes to challenging waste, like those resulting from medical facilities and operations (World Health Organization, 2014). Standardization constitutes determining the activities that define the process, formulating the solutions to repetitive actions, and issuing documentation stating these standards (Akyar, 2012). Standardization also plays a significant role in quality systems. These systems encompass organizational structures, responsibilities, processes, and implementation resources to achieve the goals of the organization (Manghani, 2011).

Quality systems are also defined by improvement, particularly with respect to stakeholder requirements (Siva et al., 2016). Siva et al. (2016) highlight that sustainability has become a requirement and that these considerations should be integrated into existing processes rather than creating new ones. Quality systems support factors like process optimization, resource efficiency, product longevity, and waste reduction through monitoring and process documentation (Carnerud et al., 2025; de Menezes et al., 2021).

SOPs are an integral part of the translation process strategy to operations. They are often written documents, that contain instructions on how a specific process can perform the same way every time it is executed (Bashatah, 2025). SOPs derive their content from expert field-based knowledge, and systematic data from physical processes. However, formulating general SOPs for the humanitarian context, such as a field hospital, brings about specific challenges. Vulnerable contexts and precarious infrastructure for WM as well as unpredictable partnerships and dynamics make standardisation a challenge (Silvestre, 2015; Tilley & Kalina, 2020).

In these SOPs, the focus is on implementing circularity processes to field hospital operations’ WM as a strategic default. The waste hierarchy serves as the basis in formulating these procedures, which is in accordance with the EU Waste Framework Directive (Directive 2008/98/EC, 2008). Circularity and CE aim to achieve efficient resource use through the 10R framework (Morseletto, 2020), as presented in Table 1. The 10R framework takes the waste hierarchy beyond WM, and integrates the whole product life cycle from material choices to end-of-life in the framework (Voudrias, 2024).

Table 1 The 10R framework

Target	Strategy
Smarter product use and manufacture	R0 – Refuse
	R1 – Rethink
	R2 – Reduce
Extend lifespan of product and its parts	R3 – Reuse
	R4 – Repair
	R5 – Refurbish
	R6 – Remanufacture
	R7 - Repurpose
Useful application of materials	R8 – Recycle
	R9 – Recovery

In this document we draw from the targets in Table 1 (Morseletto, 2020). As outlined in several WORM deliverables (e.g. D1.1, D1.2, D2.2, D3.1, D4.2), WM processes begin with strategic decisions regarding the products and their life cycles. “Refusing” non-sustainable products and materials, “rethinking” how products are actually used and how their use can be intensified, and “reducing” consumption behaviours through e.g. procurement decisions lay the basis for this target (Sharma et al., 2021). Extending products’ use through for example “repair”, “refurbish” or “repurpose” is advocated for as well. These can be achieved through for example cleaning, sterilization, component recovery, or using products for e.g. training purposes (Voudrias, 2024). Useful application of materials is well covered throughout the WORM project, in for example the procurement guidelines and the plug-and-play-framework.

Highlighting the humanitarian context of the field hospital’s operations, the 10R framework’s targets are placed into the disaster management cycle (Figure 1), which is a framework used to recognize and manage activities pre- and post-disaster (Tay et al., 2022). From a strategic perspective, mitigation and preparedness encompass strategic decisions regarding the types of materials and products are to be used in a particular operation. Tools such as the LCAs (D1.2 & D1.3) are particularly relevant here. These strategies help make needs-based decisions about product use and establish processes and partnerships to extend product life cycles through reuse and repair. These decisions significantly impact the field-based

activities, which are the main focus of this SOP. Step-by-step instructions for responsible use, maintenance, and sustainable material applications are all outlined in the document.

Figure 2 Disaster management cycle and the 10R framework

Together with D5.3, this SOP covers the initial EMTs deployed to a humanitarian operation who establish a field hospital, along with the processes required. In addition to D5.1 and D5.2, the work done within WORM has informed the FRC EMT SOPs, which have been officially certified. This raises the project’s TRL to an 8, as the concepts have been completed and qualified by an organization. The SOPs are founded on guiding principles of both humanitarian aid and medical WM.

1. Background and purpose

Field hospitals or Emergency Medical teams (EMTs) deployed in humanitarian contexts serve as essential lifelines for crisis-affected populations. However, their operations generate complex, diverse waste streams, including medical consumables, packaging, pharmaceuticals, contaminated materials, and general solid waste, all of which require safe, compliant, and environmentally responsible management.

Findings from WORM (Work Package 4, Deliverable 4.2) demonstrate that 75-90% of field hospital waste is comparable to domestic solid waste, while 10-25% constitutes hazardous waste, including sharps, infectious materials, chemicals, and pharmaceuticals. WORM’s Work Package 3 (Deliverable 3.2) shows that current waste practices, particularly open burning, unregulated incineration, and the disposal of PVC-based materials, produce significant air pollution, releasing toxic dioxins, furans, and particulate matter.

At the same time, evidence from multiple EMTs deployments shows that 10% to 30% of procured items remain unused at the end of missions due to overstocking, misaligned procurement, and short

deployment cycles. These inefficiencies increase costs and environmental impacts and undermine accountability.

This Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) operationalizes the WORM project's circular economy framework by providing practical guidance for:

- Sustainable and needs-based product use
- Reuse, maintenance, and repair of equipment
- Field-based recycling and refurbishment systems
- Structured reverse logistics
- Transparent recovery and limited handover

Drawing on WORM's Procurement Guidelines for Bio-Based Solutions (Deliverable 2.2), the SOP integrates circularity across the full product lifecycle from procurement and use to reuse, recycling, and recovery.

The purpose is to improve environmental performance, reduce waste, optimize resources, and ensure compliance with donor, environmental, and host-country requirements.

Objectives

This SOP pursues five interlinked objectives:

- **Optimize product use** by embedding sustainability into procurement, ensuring items meet real needs, and avoiding reliance on single-use disposables.
- **Promote reuse, maintenance, and repair** to extend equipment lifespan and reduce replacement costs.
- **Enable safe recycling and refurbishment** by partnering with certified providers and safely integrating local enterprises and informal waste workers.
- **Institutionalize reverse logistics** through planned systems for tracking, take-back, and recovery.
- **Support recovery and limited handover** so reusable supplies and functional equipment are reintegrated into humanitarian or host-country systems and, where appropriate, repatriated for redeployment.

Scope and applicability

This SOP applies to all field hospitals and EMTs operating in humanitarian settings. It covers the product lifecycle management process from procurement through disposal, including use, reuse, repair, refurbishment, recycling, reverse logistics, and recovery. The SOP emphasizes partnerships and coordination with host governments, ministries, humanitarian clusters, local enterprises, and informal waste pickers. It is relevant in both short-term emergency deployments and extended operations, where facilities may transition into host-country systems. It is intended for EMT logisticians, WASH staff, biomedical technicians, clinicians, and facility operational managers.

Guiding principles

- **Do No Harm:** All decisions must safeguard patients, staff, and local communities. Poor waste management creates direct risks (infections, injuries) and indirect risks (pollution, toxic exposure).
- **Circularity First:** Maximize reuse, repair, and recycling before disposal. Waste is viewed as a resource to be reintegrated into local or humanitarian systems.

- **Sustainability by Design:** Procurement prioritizes bio-based, durable, modular, and recyclable products. Use of Life Cycle Costing (LCC) ensures procurement reflects full costs, including waste management and end-of-life handling.
- **Local Integration:** Align SOP with host-country laws, infrastructure, and cultural practices. Promote local sourcing to reduce transport emissions and strengthen local resilience.
- **Accountability and Transparency:** Maintain documentation and traceability of procurement, product use, recovery, and handover.
- **Livelihood Inclusion:** Recognize informal waste pickers as stakeholders and support their integration into safe, dignified conditions.
- **Early Planning:** Reverse logistics, recovery, and exit strategies should be considered during program design, not as an afterthought at mission closure.

Roles and responsibilities

- **WASH Manager/Officer:** Leads implementation, monitors compliance, trains staff, reports to management, and coordinates with government and cluster partners.
- **Facility Management Team:** Provides infrastructure, ensures protective equipment is available, and coordinates staff vaccinations (Hepatitis A/B, Polio, Typhoid, Cholera, Tetanus).
- **Waste Handlers (cleaners):** Execute segregation, collection, and safe transfer and disposal of waste using appropriate Personal Protective Equipment (PPE).
- **Operators:** Run and maintain incinerators, autoclaves, shredders, and Volume reducers; maintain operational logs for audits.
- **Transport Staff and Drivers:** Package, label, and move hazardous materials safely, trained in spill response and emergency procedures.
- **Logistics Officer (Reverse Logistics Focal Point):** Tracks unused supplies digitally, coordinates take-back and donation processes and leads recovery planning.
- **Waste management Committees/TWGs:** Guide ethical and sustainable management of donated or surplus items by aligning practices with national and WHO standards. Advice on reuse, return, or disposal, coordinate with local stakeholders, ensure proper documentation and training, and promote knowledge sharing across deployments.
- **Community and Waste Management Partners:** Act as certified recyclers, refurbishments, and informal waste workers engaged under occupational health safeguards.

2. Integration of WORM concepts

This SOP is not a stand-alone operational tool; it represents the practical translation of WORM’s research findings, methodologies, and sustainability concepts into field-level actions. Each element of this SOP operationalizes insights, evidence, and innovations developed across other Work Packages of the WORM project. Together, these interlinkages ensure that sustainability, circularity, and accountability are embedded throughout the life cycle of EMT and field hospital operations.

Circularity and sustainable operations

The central guiding principle of this SOP is circularity, designing EMT operations so that materials, equipment, and products remain in use for as long as possible, generating minimal waste and maximizing resource value.

Circularity is achieved through:

- Reuse and refurbishment of durable medical tools and logistics assets.
- Recycling and repurposing of non-contaminated materials and packaging.

- Reverse logistics systems for recovery, redistribution, or safe repatriation.
- Planned handover and donation strategies that extend the operational life of equipment.
- Feedback loops from field missions to improve future procurement and design.

Circularity principles, derived from WORM Work Package 3 (Deliverable 3.2), are operationalized here through measurable indicators including reuse rates, recovery volumes, and recycling ratios that allow EMTs to monitor their circular performance during and after deployment.

LCCA and LCA

Drawing from the research outputs of WORM Work Package 2 (Deliverable 2.2 – Procurement Guidelines for Bio-Based Solutions), this SOP integrates Life Cycle Cost Analysis (LCCA) and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) into EMT planning, procurement, and operational processes.

- **LCCA** ensures that the total cost of ownership (procurement, maintenance, energy use, waste disposal, and end-of-life recovery) is evaluated before purchase, promoting economic efficiency and long-term sustainability.
- **LCA** assesses the environmental impact of products, from raw material extraction to disposal, enabling EMTs to select low-carbon, low-toxicity, and recyclable options.

This SOP mandates that:

- At least **50%** of procurement tenders integrate LCCA/LCA criteria.
- Procurement officers receive training in sustainability screening and documentation.
- Field-level teams record product performance and waste generation to update life cycle data.

Through these measures, EMTs ensure that cost, performance, and environmental impact are holistically balanced in every supply and operational decision.

Bio-based and low-impact procurement

Building on WORM WP2 Deliverable 2.2, this SOP supports the shift toward bio-based, modular, and recyclable materials in EMT operations. These include biodegradable personal protective equipment (PPE), recyclable packaging, reusable textiles, and medical devices designed for easy disassembly and refurbishment.

Procurement and logistics units are instructed to:

- Prioritize suppliers offering bio-based alternatives to conventional products.
- Require product origin, composition, and recyclability declarations in all tenders.
- Develop supplier take-back systems for packaging and unused stock.
- Track the proportion of bio-based vs. conventional materials used per mission.

These actions ensure that EMT supply chains contribute to environmental protection while maintaining operational effectiveness.

Circular business models and local partnerships

Findings from WORM Work Package 3 (Circularity and Innovative Business Models) are applied through the establishment of local partnerships and resource recovery mechanisms. EMTs are encouraged to engage certified local recyclers, refurbishers, and artisans to foster community-level circular economies that extend the humanitarian impact.

The SOP institutionalizes:

- Waste Management Committees (WMCs) to coordinate with local and national authorities.
- Contractual frameworks for local recycling and refurbishment services.
- Documentation of recovered material flows to support transparency and reporting.
- Community engagement mechanisms for co-managed waste zones and the inclusion of informal waste workers.

These practices transform EMT operations into catalysts for local capacity building and green economic recovery, bridging humanitarian and development objectives.

Modular infrastructure and plug-and-play systems

The modular “plug-and-play” frameworks developed under WORM Work Package 4 (Task 4.2) are embedded in this SOP to ensure that waste zones, repair units, and recovery facilities are rapidly deployable, scalable, and easily integrated with field hospital layouts.

Operational linkages include:

- Standardized waste segregation units are designed for quick assembly and disassembly.
- Modular repair and sterilization pods that connect to existing utilities.
- Mobile recycling and storage containers are adaptable to various field contexts.
- Integration of reverse logistics channels with warehouse and transport modules.

By adopting the WP4 plug-and-play framework, EMTs achieve greater operational efficiency, reduce setup times, and ensure that waste and recovery systems are integrated into the initial deployment design rather than treated as an afterthought.

3. Operational procedures

Product use and waste minimisation

Effective waste management begins at the procurement and product-use stage, where circular principles must be embedded in planning and operations. EMTs and field hospitals should adopt a lifecycle-based procurement strategy that minimizes unnecessary materials, promotes reuse, and integrates sustainability into all stages of product use and disposal. Field data from WORM WP4 (Deliverable 4.2) show that 75-90% of EMT waste is comparable to domestic waste, while only 10-25% is hazardous, indicating significant potential to reduce waste through more innovative procurement and material selection. Procurement and logistics teams must apply Life Cycle Costing (LCC) and sustainability screening criteria to select bio-based, modular, durable, and recyclable products. Over-procurement and reliance on single-use plastics must be actively discouraged. Suppliers should provide take-back or recovery agreements for packaging and equipment. Behavioral change campaigns should focus on rational PPE use to reduce overconsumption linked to post-COVID operational habits. Digitalization, including e-records, inventory management, and patient documentation, can further reduce paper waste and improve transparency.

Key Procedural Requirements:

- Integrate **sustainability and circularity** clauses in at least 50% of procurement tenders.
- Conduct **needs-based procurement** using accurate caseload forecasting to prevent overstocking.
- Apply **LCC analysis** to capture the total lifecycle and disposal costs.
- Introduce **supplier take-back clauses** for packaging and reusable devices.
- Conduct **monthly reviews** of product use and waste generation to adjust supply forecasts.

- Implement **behavioural change campaigns** to promote reusable, biodegradable, or recyclable alternatives.

Indicators

- % of tenders/Request for quotations (RFQs) including LCA and sustainability clauses.
- % of bio-based, modular, or recyclable products procured.
- % reduction in single-use plastics and non-recyclable materials.
- Volume of packaging waste reduced.

Use, reuse, and maintenance

Prolonging the lifespan of medical and logistical assets through reuse, repair, and preventive maintenance is central to sustainability and operational continuity. All equipment should be designed and managed for longevity, ease of maintenance, and modularity. Critical biomedical and electrical equipment must undergo weekly preventive maintenance, supported by standard checklists, repair logs, and spare part inventories. Biomedical engineers, local technicians, and EMT logisticians should form part of the operational team to enable field-level troubleshooting and local capacity building. Use of QR-coded manuals, digital repair guides, and remote technical assistance is encouraged to standardize maintenance practices. Reusable tools, surgical instruments, and linens must be sterilized using validated autoclaves or other approved methods. Adequate sterilization and laundry systems are mandatory before deploying reusable materials.

Key Procedural Requirements:

- Implement **weekly preventive maintenance** covering calibration, sterilization, and repair.
- Track equipment downtime and repair history through **ERP or FleetWave systems**.
- Ensure spare parts and modular replacements are pre-positioned.
- Train all relevant staff on **maintenance, disinfection, and reuse protocols**.
- Incorporate **maintenance training into induction** for biomedical and logistics personnel.
- Ensure that **laundry and sterilization systems** comply with biosafety and IPC standards.

Indicators:

- % of equipment inspected and maintained weekly/bi-weekly.
- % of reusable equipment functional at mission close.
- % of staff trained on maintenance and reuse practices.

Repair, repurpose, recycle, and refurbish

Repair, recycling, and refurbishment form the backbone of circular humanitarian logistics, reducing the environmental footprint of EMT operations and extending the lifecycles of materials. Waste segregation and recycling infrastructure must be designed to use modular “plug-and-play” frameworks developed under WORM WP4, enabling rapid setup, mobility, and safe separation of waste streams. Color-coded bins and clearly labelled segregation systems (general, recyclable, infectious, hazardous) must be used. Non-contaminated materials (e.g., disinfected bladders, water containers, or packaging) should be repurposed for secondary functions where feasible.

EMTs should partner with certified recyclers, refurbishers, and local artisans, ensuring proper documentation and occupational health safeguards. To maintain accountability, Waste Management Committees (WMCs) must oversee recycling, refurbishment, and reporting processes. Training in 3R (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle) principles and safety must be continuous and inclusive, covering both EMT staff and local partners.

Key Procedural Requirements:

- Establish **dedicated waste zones** aligned with biosafety and WORM WP4 modular standards.
- Maintain an updated list of **certified local recyclers and refurbishers**.
- Establish **Waste Management Committees** to oversee, record, and ensure compliance.
- Promote **safe repurposing of non-contaminated materials** and document all activities.
- Apply **3R principles** in all waste management SOPs and training.
- Maintain **refurbishment logs** (digital and paper-based) to record materials processed and outcomes.

Indicators

- # of healthcare facilities implementing waste segregation, and following recommended management and treatment standards
- % of total waste safely segregated by category.
- % of total waste recycled or refurbished.
- Number of certified local recycling/refurbishment partners engaged

Reverse logistics

Reverse logistics ensures the recovery, redistribution, and responsible return or disposal of unused or reusable items, converting end-of-life management into a circular process. This must be integrated into the deployment planning phase and aligned with host-country systems. Digital tracking (ERP/FleetWave) must record item movements, expiry, and storage conditions.

Local redistribution and donation should be prioritized to reduce carbon emissions and logistical costs. Suppliers' take-back and donation frameworks must be negotiated before deployment, and environmental impact assessments should be included in closure reports for repatriation cases.

Training in safe handling, infection prevention and control (IPC), and waste transport is mandatory for all staff involved.

Key Procedural Requirements:

- Integrate reverse logistics frameworks into deployment and closure planning.
- Establish **digital tracking systems** (Example: ERP, FleetWave) for high-value and expiring materials.
- Document all **returns, redistributions, and disposals** using standardized templates.
- Formalize **supplier take-back and donation agreements** before deployment.
- Collaborate with **host ministries and logistics clusters** for national alignment.
- Conduct **post-return audits** to track recovered item outcomes.

Indicators

- % of unused items recovered or redistributed.
- % of take-back or donation agreements activated.
- % of redistributions completed at least six months before expiry

Handover and donation management

At the end of deployment, EMTs must conduct handover and donation processes in a structured, transparent, and sustainable manner to ensure continuity of services, accountability to host authorities, and compliance with national and international standards.

This component is governed by the “**SOP for Handover and Donation Management of EMTs and Field Hospitals to Local Actors**” developed under **WORM Work Package 5, Task 5.2**, which provides detailed procedural and documentation templates for the safe and sustainable transition of assets. This SOP complements the existing SOP and focuses on the operational and logistical aspects that precede and enable effective handover and donation.

Handover planning must begin at mission inception and be reflected in deployment and logistics plans. The process should ensure that all donated assets, equipment, consumables, or infrastructure are functional, compatible with local systems, and maintainable over the long term. All transfers must be fully documented through chain-of-custody forms, including item descriptions, serial numbers, condition reports, and signed acknowledgements from both donor and recipient representatives. Hard-copy documentation and digital recordkeeping should be mandatory. Donations must never include obsolete, unsafe, or technologically incompatible items, as these impose maintenance and financial burdens on recipient facilities. Training, manuals, and spare parts must accompany all transferred items. Post-handover follow-up and monitoring at one month and six months should confirm operational status, user satisfaction, and any required maintenance or corrective actions.

Key Procedural Requirements:

- Follow the detailed procedures and documentation templates provided in the **WORM WP5 Task 5.2 SOP for Handover and Donation Management**.
- Establish a clear communication with response clusters (health, WASH and EMT CC).
- Integrate handover and donation planning into the initial **deployment and exit strategies**.
- Conduct **technical compatibility and functionality assessments** prior to transfer.
- Provide **user training, manuals, and spare parts** with every donation.
- Maintain **digital and hardcopy chain-of-custody records** for all assets.
- Conduct **joint verification visits** with recipient institutions during handover.
- Implement **follow-up evaluations** at one and six-months post-transfer.
- Ensure complete alignment with **WHO EMT CC guidance and national regulatory frameworks** for Health and WASH.

Indicators:

- # of handovers completed using Task 5.2 SOP templates and documentation.
- % of donated assets are fully functional and in use after three months.
- % of handovers completed with recipient training provided.
- # of follow-up/post-handover monitoring reports completed.

4. Health, safety, and risk mitigation

All waste management staff must be vaccinated, with Hepatitis B and Tetanus as minimum requirements. PPE must be provided, and its correct use reinforced through training and pictorial guidance. Waste zones must be fenced, ventilated, and secured against unauthorized access. Monthly health and safety audits must be carried out, with corrective actions implemented and documented. Presented here is a sample monthly health and safety audit checklist for WM operations.

Facility Name: _____ **Month/Year:** _____ **Location:**
 _____ **Date:** _____

Completed by: _____ **Designation:** _____

Section A. Staff Health and Safety Compliance

#	Item / Requirement	Verification Method	Yes / No / Partial	Comments / Corrective/Mitigation Actions
1	All waste management and support staff vaccinated (Hepatitis B, Tetanus minimum).	Staff records / vaccination cards	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	
2	Health checks conducted for staff exposed to infectious or chemical waste.	Medical reports / interviews	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	
3	Staff trained in safe waste handling, IPC, spill response, and use of PPE.	Training records	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	
4	PPE (gloves, masks, boots, goggles, aprons) available and in good condition.	Visual check	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	
5	Correct use of PPE observed during daily operations.	Observation	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	
6	Eye-wash stations, first aid kits, and sharps injury kits available and accessible.	Physical check	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	
7	Reported incidents or injuries logged and reviewed within 24 hours.	Incident log	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	

Section B. Waste Handling and Zoning

#	Item / Requirement	Verification Method	Yes / No / Partial	Comments / Corrective/Mitigation Actions
8	Waste segregation by color code (infectious, sharps, recyclable, general) followed correctly.	Observation / bins	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	
9	All waste containers labeled with hazard symbols and filled \leq two-thirds capacity.	Observation	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	
10	Waste zones fenced, lockable, and restricted to trained staff only.	Observation	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	
11	Waste storage area protected from weather, pests, and flooding.	Observation	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	

12	Ventilation adequate and signage visible (biohazard, PPE required).	Observation	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	
13	Handwashing or decontamination station available near waste area.	Observation	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	

Section C. Equipment Operation and Maintenance

#	Item / Requirement	Verification Method	Yes / No / Partial	Comments / Corrective/Mitigation Actions
14	Incinerator/autoclave/shredder operational and maintained.	Maintenance log	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	
15	Operators trained and competent in use of treatment equipment.	Training record	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	
16	Daily operational logs are maintained for treatment processes.	Logbook review	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	
17	Emission/smoke levels within acceptable limits; ash disposed safely.	Observation	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	
18	Fire extinguishers are available and functional near waste/treatment zones.	Physical check	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	

Section D. Emergency Preparedness and Documentation

#	Item / Requirement	Verification Method	Yes / No / Partial	Comments / Corrective/Mitigation Actions
19	Emergency contact list posted visibly in waste area.	Observation	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	
20	Spill kits available and complete (absorbent, disinfectant, gloves, masks, bags).	Observation	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	

21	Emergency evacuation routes clearly marked and unobstructed.	Observation	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	
22	Fire drills conducted in the last 6 months.	Records / staff interviews	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	
23	Monthly safety checklist completed, and corrective actions tracked.	Checklist log	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partial	

Section E. Summary of Observations and Corrective Actions

Findings / Issues Identified	Immediate Actions Taken	Responsible Person	Timeline for Completion

Review and Approval

Name	Designation	Signature	Date
WASH Manager/Officer			
Facility Manager / EMT Team Lead			
Safety & Quality Officer			

5. Adoption and upkeep

Barriers and mitigation strategies

Financial, technical, regulatory, and market barriers can limit the adoption of sustainable practices. Higher upfront costs for sustainable products can be mitigated by applying life-cycle costing and advocating for donor support. Limited awareness can be mitigated through training and awareness campaigns. Technical capacity must be strengthened through procurement and logistics training and partnerships with local technicians. Regulatory barriers can be reduced by engaging with authorities to ensure compliance with hygiene and safety regulations. Market gaps require supporting local suppliers and pooling demand to shape markets for sustainable products.

Table 2 Barriers and mitigation strategies

Barrier Category	Description of the Barrier	Mitigation Strategies	Relevant WORM Linkages
Financial Constraints	Sustainable, modular, or bio-based products often have higher upfront costs; limited budgets for repair/refurbishment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Apply Life Cycle Costing (LCC) rather than unit-price comparisons. - Advocate with donors for sustainability line-items. - Use pooled procurement mechanisms. 	Bio-based procurement; circular business models
Limited Awareness & Behavioural Resistance	Staff may prefer disposables (post-COVID habits); limited awareness of reuse/recycling benefits.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conduct ongoing awareness and behaviour change campaigns. - Integrate sustainability modules into induction training. - Provide visual job aids and reminders. 	behavioural drivers and causal loops
Technical Capacity Gaps	Limited availability of biomedical engineers, technicians, or skilled waste handlers; inadequate repair infrastructure.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Train local technicians and incorporate them into EMT teams. - Develop troubleshooting manuals, QR-code guides. - Stock essential spare parts and modular components. 	infrastructure and plug-and-play systems
Supply Chain & Market Limitations	Few suppliers for bio-based or recyclable products; limited recycling/refurbishment markets; shortages of spare parts.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conduct local market assessments early. - Build partnerships with recyclers, refurbishes, SMEs. - Encourage suppliers offering take-back schemes. 	Market analysis, circular business models
Regulatory & Compliance Barriers	National rules may restrict reuse, cross-border recycling, or donation of refurbished equipment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engage authorities early in mission planning. - Align SOPs with national waste regulations. - Document all compliance processes transparently. 	Policy integration and standardization
Waste Infrastructure Limitations	Lack of compliant incinerators, autoclaves, or safe landfill options; weak municipal waste services.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish modular waste zones using plug and play designs. - Prioritize non-burn technologies (autoclave/microwave). - Partner with local waste operators with capacity-building. 	Plug-and-play infrastructure, 3R systems
Operational Realities of EMT Deployments	Short deployment cycles restrict long-term waste strategies; rapid scale-up leads to overstocking and excess waste.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrate reverse logistics planning at deployment start. - Use digital tracking for stock monitoring. 	Reverse logistics loops, procurement planning

		- Coordinate early donation/recovery plans with partners.	
Data, Monitoring & Documentation Gaps	Limited digital tracking; inconsistent waste logs; weak feedback loops across operations.	- Use digital dashboards for real-time tracking. - Conduct quarterly Quality, Safety and Environment (QSE) audits. - Standardize forms and chain-of-custody documentation.	Coordination, circularity indicators

Monitoring, reporting, and learning

Digital dashboards should support monitoring to track product flows, waste generation, and recovery. Quarterly or bi-annually Quality, Safety, and Environment (QSE) audits must be conducted, and findings shared with partners. Environmental impacts should be measured, where feasible, using life-cycle analysis, and lessons learned from deployments should be captured in after-action reviews to refine SOPs over time.

Indicators:

- *Number of audits conducted.*
- *% of products assessed with Life Cycle Analysis.*

Mandatory records include:

- Waste segregation and treatment logs,
- Reverse logistics and recovery reports,
- Handover/donation checklists,
- Training registers,
- Compliance and safety audits.

Both paper and digital formats must be maintained for accountability.

All staff must receive induction training on SOP compliance, with refresher sessions at least quarterly. Training must cover sustainable procurement, circular economic principles, safe recycling, and occupational health and safety. SOPs should be adapted to local contexts and validated during field trials to ensure feasibility and effectiveness.

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ANNEX 1 – SOPs gathered

SOP#	Waste Types Covered	Segregation Rules	Storage Requirements	Transport Guidelines	Treatment Methods	Disposal Methods	Compliance References
SOP1	General, Medical, Sharps, Pharmaceutical	Color-coded bins, sharps in puncture-proof containers	Temporary storage in secure area	Dedicated containers, PPE for handlers	Incineration, municipal disposal	Incineration, burial	WHO EMT standards
SOP2	General, Medical, Sharps, Pharmaceutical	Segregation at source	Secure storage area	Transport with PPE	Incineration, encapsulation	Burial, incineration	WHO EMT standards
SOP3	General waste	Black bags for non-hazardous	Secure storage	Internal transfer	Controlled burning	Municipal disposal	WHO EMT standards
SOP4	Clinical infectious waste	Yellow bags	Secure storage	Internal transfer	High-temp incineration	Ash burial	WHO EMT standards
SOP5	Pharmaceutical waste	Separate containers	Hazardous waste section	Internal transfer	Encapsulation	Landfill	WHO EMT standards
SOP6	Sharps	Puncture-proof containers	Secure storage	Internal transfer	Incineration	Encapsulation	WHO EMT standards
SOP7	All waste streams	Color-coded bins	Temporary storage	Dedicated wheeled containers	Depends on type	Depends on type	WHO EMT standards
SOP8	All waste streams	Color-coded zones	Restricted-access zone	Internal transfer	Incineration, encapsulation	Burial	WHO EMT standards
SOP9	Incinerator ash	N/A	Dedicated ash pit	Internal transfer	N/A	Burial in ash pit	WHO EMT standards
SOP10	Medical waste	Color-coded bins	Secure storage	Internal transfer	Incineration, disinfection	Landfill	WHO EMT standards
SOP11	Packaging, materials	Segregation by type	Secure storage	Tracked transport	Return to suppliers	Recycling	Sustainability standards

SOP12	General, Medical, Pharmaceutical, Sharps	Color-coded bins	Secure storage	Internal transfer	Incineration, autoclaving	Landfill, encapsulation	WHO HCWM
SOP13	Fecal sludge, lab waste	Segregation by hazard	BSL-2 lab storage	Internal transfer	Autoclaving, chemical treatment	Concrete immobilization	APHA, WHO
SOP14	Pharmaceutical waste	Separate containers	Secure hazardous storage	Tracked transport	High-temp incineration, coprocessing	Encapsulation, engineered landfill	WHO
SOP15	Medical waste	11 waste classes, color-coded bins	Secure storage	Internal transfer	Incineration, autoclaving	Landfill, encapsulation	WHO
SOP16	Medical waste	Pre-segregated at source	Secure storage	Dedicated vehicles with hazard signage	Depends on type	Depends on type	WHO
SOP17	Medical waste	Pre-segregated at source	Secure storage	Internal transfer	Incineration ($\geq 1050^{\circ}\text{C}$), autoclaving	Landfill, encapsulation	WHO
SOP18	General, Medical, Sharps	Color-coded bags	Secure storage	Internal transfer	Incineration, chlorine disinfection	Burial	WHO
SOP19	Vaccine vials, sharps, PPE	Separate vials and sharps	Secure storage	Dedicated vehicles	Disinfection, autoclaving	Incineration, encapsulation	WHO COVID-19 guidance
SOP20	General, Medical, Hazardous, Organic	Color-coded bags (black, blue, red, brown)	Temporary storage area with sections	Dedicated wheeled containers	Incineration, concrete encapsulation	Landfill, burial	Local regulations, WHO

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